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Operation experience in a TRL7 Calcium Looping plant using biomass as a fuel in the oxy-fired circulating fluidised bed calciner

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Abstract

This work reports some of the initial tests carried out in the 1.7 MW_{th} “la Pereda” Calcium Looping pilot after being re-furnished during 2023 to allow biomass firing in the oxy-fired circulating fluidised bed combustor-calciner. The TRL7 pilot can treat up to 1% of the flue gases of the 50 MWe power plant of Hunosa. This work is part of the EU funded CaLby2030 project, that intends, among other objectives, to demonstrate at TRL7 Calcium Looping using Circulating Fluidised Beds, CFB-CaL, in a range of carbon intensive industries [1]. The first tests conducted under oxy-combustion of biomass pellets in the calciner is reported, including campaigns devoted to test at TRL7 the capability of CFB-CaL systems to reach CO₂ capture efficiencies in the carbonator approaching 99%, by cooling the exit area do the carbonator and by ensuring a sufficient reactivity of the Ca-solids in that region, feeding a small “polishing flow” of Ca(OH)₂ powder when needed.

Keywords: CO₂ capture, Calcium looping, oxy-fuel combustion, biomass

1. Introduction

Calcium Looping (CaL) is a CO₂ capture technology that uses CaO as a sorbent for the capture of CO₂ in a carbonator reactor at around 650°C, forming CaCO₃. In a subsequent energy intensive calcination step, a highly-concentrated stream of CO₂ is obtained while regenerating CaO at temperatures around 900°C. The CaO particles are therefore cycled many times in a continuous calcium loop. One advantage of such process is that the heat required to drive the endothermic calcination of CaCO₃ could be effectively recovered at boiler temperatures in the carbonator, thus allowing for low energy penalties[2]. Many process, reactor and material alternatives involving CaL reactions have been published in the past few years, with about 50 review papers published on the CaL topic. Tan et al. [3] have recently compiled the characteristics and status of pilot testing facilities from 1 kW_{th} to 20 MW_{th}, with the largest pilot

reporting results rated at the MW_{th} scale [4-12]. Most of the large pilots are characterised by the use of two interconnected Circulating Fluidised Bed (CFB) reactors (Figure 1, right), as it was early recognized that post-combustion CaL using this type of reactors is the most suitable configuration to deal with the large volumetric flows of gases in and out of the reactors and solids circulation between reactors. CFB-CaL reactors benefits from their similarity with CFBC boilers in terms of material characteristics, solid circulation rates, gas flows rates and a combustion atmosphere (facilitating a safe interconnection).

Figure 1. General view of La Pereda pilot plant (left) and general scheme of a CFB-CaL system (right).

The rapid decline in Europe of coal-based power generation in the last decade represented a decisive set back to the scale-up plans of CFB-CaL technology. However, new plans are in place to adapt CFB-CaL technologies to major industrial sectors (i.e., cement and steel) and future power generation combustion systems using residual biomass and waste under a recent Horizon Europe R&D project [1]. Similarly to commercial CFBC boilers, CFB-CaL systems can in principle use a wide variety of fuels in the calciner, including biomass or other carbon-neutral fuels. Some works have reported in the literature results from pilots using biomass and solid recovery fuel in the oxy-fired calciner [13-15]. The use of this kind of fuels implies that CFB-CaL systems can result into negative values if the CO₂ evolved from the calciner is permanently stored, or provide a source of renewable CO₂ for the manufacture of CO₂-based synthetic products.

Reaching very high capture efficiencies (i.e., capturing over 99% of CO₂) in post-combustion systems operating at atmospheric pressure is challenging due to the reduced driving force of CO₂ towards the exit of the capture device, whether this is an absorption tower, a bed of solid sorbents, or a membrane. CFB-CaL carbonators face a similar challenge, as most of the active part of the CaO arriving to the reactor has already reacted with CO₂ in the dense region at the bottom of the carbonator [16]. In principle, this makes difficult for the particles to further react with the residual CO₂ diluted in the flue gases at the top of the carbonator. However, early experiments by Fan et al. [17] and results from a drop tube carbonator reported elsewhere [18] have demonstrated that nascent CaO (in particular if this comes from the in situ decomposition of Ca(OH)₂) has an extremely high reactivity towards CO₂ in a wide range of carbonation temperatures. Therefore, a variant of the CFB-CaL system of Figure 1 has been proposed by CSIC [19], involving a carbonator with enhanced cooling capabilities to operate with a cooler region of enhanced carbonation at

the top of the reactor as represented in Figure 2-left (for simplicity, other heat transfer equipment in the CaL system is omitted).

Figure 2. Left) Basic scheme of the carbonator configuration targeted to achieve high CO₂ capture efficiencies. Right) Maximum CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator of a CaL system as a function of temperature (for an inlet gas with 12%_v CO₂, using the equation of Baker for the equilibrium of CO₂ on CaO [20]).

The purpose of the additional heat exchange represented in Figure 2-left is to reduce the temperatures in that region to well below 600°C, so that the CO₂-CaO equilibrium allows deeper decarbonisation of the flue-gases. For example, as represented in Figure 2-right, for a typical flue gas inlet of 12%_v CO₂, thermodynamics allows 99% capture efficiency when the carbonator is designed to operate at 550 °C. However, this comes with some trade-offs when compared to state-of-the-art CFB-CaL systems, usually designed to achieve CO₂ capture efficiencies of 90% with the carbonator operating at 650 °C. First, the heat demand in the oxy-fired calciner would increase, as more energy would be needed to heat up the solids coming from the carbonator. Another drawback is the decrease in the maximum CO₂ carrying capacity of CaO as the carbonation temperature reduces [21] which will demand higher solid circulation rates to transport the CO₂ from the carbonator to the calciner. Finally, the lower temperatures in the carbonator will slightly reduce the energy efficiency of the steam cycle recovering energy from the carbonator, and therefore, increase the required area of the boiler tubes.

To counteract these impacts, the carbonator of Figure 2-left requires the generation of an axial temperature gradient to produce a temperature drop of about 100 °C in the top region. This can be achieved through the combined effect of a second heat exchanger, by means of the injection of the make-up flow of limestone at that point or even by quenching with liquid water. With this approach, high carbonation temperatures will be maintained in the dense bottom region of the CFB carbonator, where the intense solid mixing and good gas-solid contact will allow most of the carbonation and heat extraction to take place. In any case, it is important that the CaO material entrained upwards to that cooled region has sufficient reactivity towards CO₂ to approach equilibrium in the carbonator exit region.

As part of the recent Horizon Europe R&D project [1], many small retrofits have been implemented on La Pereda CFB-CaL pilot plant (shown in Figure 1) to make it operational again and to test for the first time in this pilot the oxy-combustion of wood pellets in the calciner as well as the new process variant in the carbonator proposed above. The purpose of this paper is to report new set of results of a three week-long experimental campaign that demonstrate at TRL7 the viability of enhanced carbonation by adjusting the temperature profile as shown in Figure 2, with CO₂ capture efficiencies over 99% in the carbonator while operating the calciner under oxy-combustion of biomass.

Nomenclature

$E_{\text{Carb eq}}$: the maximum capture efficiency limited by the equilibrium
 E_{carb} : CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator
 f_a : fraction of active solids in the carbonator
 F_{Ca} : molar circulation rate between carbonator and calciner reactors
 k_s : constant reaction rate that depends on the limestone used
 n_{Ca} : the inventory of solids in the carbonator
 t^* : time needed to increase the carbonate content from X_{calc} to X_{ave}
 T_{carb} : average carbonator reactor temperature
 T_{DZ} : temperature in the bottom dense zone of the carbonator
 T_{LZ} : temperature in the upper lean zone of the carbonator
 X_{ave} : CO₂ carrying capacity
 X_{calc} : carbonate content of the solids coming from the calciner
 X_{carb} : carbonate content of the solids leaving the carbonator
 τ_{active} : active space time
 ϕ : gas-solid contacting factor

2. Experimental

The results presented in this work have been obtained during several experimental campaigns carried out in La Pereda 1.7 MW_{th} pilot plant shown in Figure 1 left (a more detailed description of this facility can be found in elsewhere [5], [22]). This pilot can treat a slip of the flue gas produced in an existing CFB power plant. However, due to a long shutdown of this power plant, flue gas was not available and the gas fed into the carbonator during these experimental campaigns has been produced by mixing air with CO₂ coming from a cryogenic tank. The main core of the facility is two CFB reactors, a carbonator and a calciner, with a height of 15 m and internal diameters of 0.65 and 0.75 m, respectively. These reactors are interconnected through two loop seals. Typical gas velocities inside the reactors are 2-6 m/s, typical of CFB boilers.

Table 1. Range of operating conditions and main variables during the tests reported in this work.

Average temperature in the carbonator, T_{CB}	°C	530-660
Superficial velocity at the carbonator	m/s	2.5-4.0
Inventory of solids in the carbonator	kg/m ²	350-650
Inlet CO ₂ volume fraction at the carbonator inlet		0.03-0.14
Maximum CO ₂ carrying capacity of the solids, X_{ave}		0.10-0.40
Average temperature in the calciner, T_{CC}	°C	840-945
Superficial velocity at the calciner	m/s	3.0-5.5
Inventory of solids in the calciner	kg/m ²	50-250
O ₂ volume fraction in the oxidant		0.30-0.40
Biomass mass flow rate	kg/h	250-450
CO ₂ capture efficiency, E_{CO_2}		0.60-0.995

The temperature in the carbonator can be modified using bayonet tubes installed in the upper part of the reactor. The tubes can be moved up and down to modify the heat extraction surface area. The calciner has an inlet close to the grid for the feeding of fuel and limestone. The fuel can be burnt under oxy-firing conditions by using a mixture of O₂/CO₂ fed from cryogenic gas tanks. The composition of the gas entering and leaving the reactors is measured continuously using four gas analyzers. The composition of the solids circulating in the system is determined periodically by taking solids samples at different ports located along the facility.

Several small modifications were carried out before the experimental campaigns in order to make the pilot plant operational again after a long shut down and to adapt it to the new operation conditions. These were mainly related with the upgrade of the gas analysis system and some repairs in the solid circulation system. During these experimental campaigns, pellets of biomass were used as fuel (50.7 %C_{wt}, 6.0 %H_{wt}, 34.6 %O_{wt}, 8.4 %H₂O_{wt}, LHV= 19.1 MJ/kg) as the existing fuel feeding system can handle with this kind of fuels after tuning the operational parameters. Table 1 summarizes the main operation conditions during the tests reported in this work.

3. Results

Some initial tests were carried out to test the operability of the pilot plant using biomass as fuel. Figure 3 shows an example of such test with the main variables. These corresponds to a typical experiment in which the calciner was operated under oxy-fuel conditions by using biomass pellets as fuel. After an initial period to preheat the pilot at temperatures above 800 °C in the calciner (not shown in the graph for simplicity), the combustion conditions in the calciner are switched from air to oxy-fuel with an average oxygen concentration of 37% v in the oxidant (at 7:40). As a result, there is a sharp increase in the CO₂ concentration at the outlet of the calciner (see Figure 3 top). Regarding the carbonator, the gas fed into the reactor is changed from air to a flue gas with a CO₂ concentration of 11.0 % v at 8:00 (Figure 3 bottom). After a short period, the average temperature in the calciner and the carbonator was stabilized and maintained at values around 935 °C and 615 °C, respectively. This was achieved by burning an average biomass flow rate of 365 kg/h (resulting into a thermal input of 1.94 MW_{th}) with an excess of oxygen at the outlet of the calciner below 5% v. During this experiment, the gas velocities in the reactors were maintained constant at 3.3 and 3.8 m/s in the carbonator and calciner, respectively. Under these conditions the circulation of solids between reactors was 1.4 kg/s, with solid inventories of 570 and 195 kg/m² in the carbonator and calciner, measured from the pressure drop readings. Figure 3 bottom shows the CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator which is maintained above 0.95.

Figure 3. Example of an experimental CO₂ capture test with oxy-fuel combustion of biomass in the calciner.

After these initial tests, several experiments were carried out to demonstrate the viability of the approach shown in Figure 2 to achieve CO₂ capture efficiencies above 0.99. For this purpose, the carbonator was operated with a wide range of temperatures as shown in Table 1. Moreover, most of these tests were carried out with a high make up flow of CaCO₃ fed into the calciner to operate the system with a sorbent with high CO₂ carrying capacity (\bar{X}_{ave}) ensuring a sufficient flow of active CaO material in the upper zone of the carbonator. Figure 4 shows an example of an experimental period aimed to achieve extremely high CO₂ capture efficiencies. For this specific test, the low

temperatures in the carbonator were obtained by feeding a flue gas with a low CO_2 concentration (5.8%_v), thus minimizing the heat generated by the carbonation. Moreover, the heat extraction was maximized by fully inserting with the four water-cooled bayonet tube into the carbonator. In addition, the conditions were adjusted to operate with a high excess of active sorbent ($F_{\text{Ca}}X_{\text{ave}}$) respect to the molar CO_2 flow (F_{CO_2}) fed into the carbonator ($F_{\text{Ca}}X_{\text{ave}}/F_{\text{CO}_2}$ of 1.8). The inventory of solids in the carbonator during this test was 495 kg/m^2 , which presented a typical distribution in CFB reactors, with the presence of a dense zone in the bottom of the reactor and a lean zone in the upper part (see Figure 4b). As shown in Figure 4a, from 12:30 to 13:20, the temperature in the carbonator was maintained constant. The temperature profile along the reactor during this period is shown in Figure 4c (white dots). As can be seen, there is homogeneous temperature of around $570 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the bottom dense zone. From this point there is sharp drop in the temperature profile with an average value of $475 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in the upper lean. During this initial period, a CO_2 capture efficiency of 0.995 was achieved in the carbonator as shown in Figure 4a. Then, the bayonet tubes in the carbonator were partially removed to reduce the heat extraction at 13:20. As result the temperature in the reactor increased during the second period, especially in the upper lean zone (from 475 up to $525 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) resulting into a decrease on the CO_2 capture efficiency as can be seen in Figure 4a.

Figure 4. a) Example of the effect of carbonator temperature on the carbonation efficiency, b) and c) inventory of solids and temperature profile along the carbonator (grey dots: from 12:30 to 13:20; white dots: from 14:00 to 14:30).

Using the temperature profiles along the carbonator, two different average zones with their respective average temperatures were defined to facilitate the data interpretation that follows. One corresponds to the average temperature in the bottom dense zone of the carbonator, T_{DZ} (from 0 to 3 meters above the grid) and the other to the temperature in the upper lean zone, T_{LZ} (from 8 to 15 meters above the grid). These two temperatures, represented in Figure 4a, were used to calculate the maximum capture efficiency that can be achieved considering CO_2 partial pressure given by the equilibrium ($E_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq-TLZ}}$ and $E_{\text{CO}_2 \text{ eq-TDZ}}$, respectively in Figure 4a). As can be seen, the experimental capture efficiency matches the maximum efficiency given by the equilibrium considering the temperature in the upper lean zone, while it clearly exceeds that limited by the temperature in the dense bed. This can be seen clearly during the second period operating at higher temperature. In this case, the experimental CO_2 capture efficiency was 0.985 while the temperature in the dense bed only allows for a maximum capture of 0.915.

To interpret the observations presented above in a more quantitative manner, a basic 0D reactor model has been used, adapted from previous works where it was developed for more standard CFB-CaL experiments [5, 23]. The basic 0D model assumes that the solid phase behaves as a perfect mix reactor while the gas phase can be considered as a plug flow reactor [24]. It also assumes the reaction rate of the particles is constant until the maximum carbonate conversion (X_{ave}) is achieved, being zero and after that point [23, 25]. According to the temperature and solid profiles, as shown in Figure 4, the carbonator is assumed to be composed of two zones, one dense zone located at bottom part

and one lean zone in the upper part, operating at two different temperatures, T_{DZ} and T_{LZ} . It can be argued that the mixing of solids between these two zones is sufficiently intense to assume that the whole inventory of solids in the carbonator is perfectly mixed respect to the solid composition, but sufficiently limited to allow the observed difference in temperatures between the two zones when the cooling capacity in the upper part is sufficiently intense. On the other hand, the gas phase is considered as two plug flow reactors connected in series. With these simplifying assumptions, the following CO_2 mass balance closure can be solved for each zone (see also Figure 5a):

$$F_{\text{CO}_2\text{in},i} E_{\text{carb},i} = n_{\text{Ca},i} f_a \left(\frac{dX}{dt} \right)_{\text{reactor},i} = n_{\text{Ca},i} f_a k_s \phi X_{\text{ave}} \left(v_{\text{CO}_2} - v_{\text{CO}_2,\text{eq}} \right)_i \quad (1)$$

where $F_{\text{CO}_2\text{in},i}$ is the molar flow of CO_2 entering each zone, $E_{\text{carb},i}$ is the CO_2 capture efficiency, $n_{\text{Ca},i}$ is the inventory of solids, k_s is an apparent constant reaction rate which has a value of 0.36s^{-1} for the limestone used in this work [5], the average CO_2 concentration and $f_{a,i}$ is the fraction of active solids which is calculated as follow, from the residence time distribution curve of a well-mixed reactor:

$$f_{a,i} = \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_i^*}{F_{\text{Ca}}}} \right) \quad (2)$$

being n_{Ca} the total inventory of solids, F_{Ca} the molar flow rate entering the carbonator and t_i^* the time needed to achieve the maximum CO_2 carrying capacity under the reaction conditions in each zone:

$$t_i^* = (X_{\text{ave}} - X_{\text{calc}}) / (k_s \phi (v_{\text{CO}_2} - v_{\text{CO}_2\text{eq}})) \quad (3)$$

Figure 5b compares the experimental CO_2 capture efficiency and the values calculated with the model including a wider range of operation conditions (e.g., inventory of solids, temperature, CO_2 inlet concentrations, etc.). The data shown in this figure corresponds to experimental periods in which there was sufficient flow of active sorbent entering the carbonator ($F_{\text{Ca}} X_{\text{ave}} / F_{\text{CO}_2} > 1.3$).

Figure 5. a) Scheme of the CFB carbonator with the main variables involved. b) Comparison of the experimental CO_2 capture efficiency and the calculated values.

A good agreement can be observed between both values. These results highlight the need to fulfil two simultaneous conditions to achieve a deep decarbonisation in the carbonator of a CFB-CaL system: a temperature around 550°C (or below) in the upper part of the reactor to overcome thermodynamic limitations, and a sufficient flowrate of active sorbent in the upper region of the carbonator. As indicated above, this second requirement has been achieved in this

work by using large make up flows of limestone in order to ensure the presence at the top of the carbonator of an excess of active CaO a sorbent with a high CO₂ carrying capacity (X_{ave}). For most post-combustion applications (except in cement or lime plants where the CaO-rich purge is a co-product and high make up flows will be used), this approach could be too demanding (in terms of high operating costs). However, there are planned retrofits in La Pereda pilot plant includes the injection of a Ca(OH)₂ polishing flow, allowing to reach such high CO₂ capture rates with moderate values of make-up flow of limestone.

4. Conclusions

A novel strategy to increase the CO₂ capture efficiency in the carbonator of a Calcium Looping system using CFB reactors has been experimentally tested in this work. This consists in the cooling of the upper part of the carbonator to create a low temperature zone and avoid the equilibrium limits on the minimum CO₂ concentration achievable. For this purpose, experiments in a TRL7 CFB-CaL pilot have been carried out operating the calciner under typical oxy-fuel conditions burning biomass at a rate of 2.0 MW_{th} and high make up flows of limestone ($F_{Ca}X_{ave}/F_{CO_2} > 1.3$). The results confirm that it is possible to reach CO₂ capture efficiencies above 0.99 by ensuring that the temperature at the outlet of the carbonator is sufficient low (<550 °C) and there is enough sorbent available in the cooled zone. The results have been successfully interpreted using a basic model that considers two reaction zones in the carbonator. Future retrofits in the La Pereda pilot plant are planned to feed Ca(OH)₂ in the upper part of the carbonator to allow the injection of active sorbent in this zone and reach high CO₂ capture rates.

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